

CORH2, a new medium-duration rice hybrid

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Increasing the yield potential of rice is one of the frontier projects in rice breeding. The development and use of hybrid rice is one approach by which rice productivity can be increased. The Paddy Breeding Station in TNAU, Coimbatore, started research on hybrid rice in 1979 and released the first hybrid, CORH1, in 1994. Another hybrid, CORH2, a medium-duration rice, was released in January 1998 for commercial cultivation.

CORH2 was developed by the three-line system using a cytoplasmic genic male sterile (CMS) line, maintainer line, and restorer line (A/B/R). The parents of this hybrid are IR58025A and C20R. CORH2 has a duration of 125 d, grows up to 95 cm, and has high tillering ability (15 productive tillers hill⁻¹).

Average grain number is 230 panicle⁻¹ and 1000-grain weight is 24 g. CORH2 has medium grains and white rice kernels. It is suitable for July-October sowing in Tamil Nadu. Its average grain yield is 5.1 t ha⁻¹ in salt-affected soils, which is 23% higher than that of saline-tolerant CO 43 (4.2 t ha⁻¹) and 28% more than TRY1

(4.0 t ha⁻¹). On average, it yields 6.1 t ha⁻¹, which is 20% higher than ADT39 (5.0 t ha⁻¹).

Table 1 presents the overall performance of CORH2 under different trials. Its biological yield was 3.8 t ha⁻¹ (6.0 t grains and 7.8 t straw). It had a 20% higher grain yield over ADT39. This hybrid had the highest yield (11.7 t ha⁻¹) in one adaptive research trial in farmers' fields. Table 2 shows its quality characteristics. It is moderately susceptible to tungro virus, blast, and whitebacked planthopper under field and controlled conditions.

Table 1. Overall performance of CORH2 compared with ADT39.

Trial	Trials no.	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
		CORH2	ADT39
Station trials	6	6.7	5.6
Multilocation trial, 1995	6	5.2	4.2
Multilocation trial, 1996	6	5.0	4.2
Large-scale demonstration, 1996	19	6.2	5.2
Adaptive research trial, 1996	47	7.1	6.0
National hybrid rice trial, 1996	9	6.2	6.1 (Jaya)
Mean	93	6.1	5.0

Table 2. Quality characteristics of hybrid CORH2.

<i>Physical characteristics</i>		
Milling - Endosperm (%)		79.9
Husk (%)		20.1
Polishing - White rice (%)		71.2
<i>Cooking characteristics</i>		
Cooking time (min)		13.14
Volume expansion ratio		4.8
Water absorption ratio		3.3
Length elongation ratio		1.9
Breadth elongation ratio		1.7
<i>Chemical characteristics</i>		
Moisture (%)		12.8
Starch (%)		61.2
Protein (%)		8.2

Evaluation of rice hybrids in different agroclimatic zones of Andhra Pradesh

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We evaluated nine experimental rice hybrids of different maturity durations for yield under diverse agroclimatic zones of Andhra Pradesh during the 1993 wet season. Test locations included Palem (southern Telangana zone), Warangal (north Telangana zone), Nandyal (scarce rainfall zone), Ragolu (north coastal zone), Maruteru, and Bapatla (Krishna-Godavari zone).

Rice hybrids were compared with one common check (IR64) and two local checks in a randomized block design with three replications. A 20 × 10-cm spacing with a plot size of 10 m² was adopted. Transplanting was done with one to two seedlings hill⁻¹. Data were analyzed and are shown in the table.

At Palem, seven hybrids recorded significantly higher grain yield over the

best check IR64 (6.2 t ha⁻¹). The yield advantage of different hybrids ranged from 1.7 to 3.2 t ha⁻¹. At Warangal, hybrids MTU HR 2020 and MTU HR 2002 outyielded the best check (Kavya) by 0.9 and 0.7 t ha⁻¹, respectively. Five hybrids significantly outyielded the best check, BPT 3291, at Nandyal. Four of nine hybrids yielded more than 9 t ha⁻¹ with 1.7 (MTU HR 2015) to 2.5 (MTU HR 2020) t ha⁻¹ higher yields